

Life phenomena include contradiction due to renormalizing ambivalence adaptively by figure-8 loop circling positive limit cycle and negative limit cycle generated by the system separation of limit cycle by the fluctuation of relativity, can deal with the contradiction by perception generated through cooperation of internal and external renormalization of relative fluctuation. This describing model represents the mechanism and function such like rolling the process of deepening dissipative structure for twist of space-time, combining and separating fluctuation, connecting 0 and ∞ , three-dimensional rotation of a sigmoid curves about a horizontal axis, fluctuation of relative intentionality and request between dissipative structure, recombinant connection of ambivalence and communication, and which is abstracted to the describing model of bilobed structure in torus structure which is topological analogous about the self and environment.

Life phenomena as a system cooperating of deepening process of relative dissipative structure adaptively organize and are organized by adaptive spatiotemporal paths in real and imaginary space-time, contact with the circulation of 0 and ∞ on the edge of chaos, store the memory of the world through the communication between entropy and space-time, renormalized to the progressed twist which is cooperating ambivalence of entropy and space-time cooperative by reverse of the process of deepening relative dissipative structure through the irreversible emergence in real and imaginary space-time by cooperation of 0 and ∞ in space-time,

Life phenomena are thought to get relative dissipative structures cooperated in space-time, by the fluctuation of the relativity between entropy and space-time through the fluctuation on the surface of spherical structure. Such a mechanism could be analogous to the autoregressive wave curve, the cooperation of internal and external renormalization in spherical structure and combination and separation of the fluctuation, and it is thought to be related to the mechanism of deepening relative dissipative structures in space-time generated by the separation of the system and cross circulation of two different orbits in quantum mechanics, topological geometry and astrophysics.

For describing about the life phenomena, the dynamic equilibrium (S, Fukuoka), the fluctuation (F, Ohsawa), dissipative structure (Prigogine, Ilya), renormalization (Y, Ohno), communication, adaptively organizing the ambivalence and paradox are thought to be important. Accordingly, how about considering of a concept of relativity of entropy in existence and cognition as one for connecting all of these?

It is considered to be a general description model for life phenomena of deepening the functional edge of chaos through the cooperation of 0 and ∞ . 0 and ∞ are thought to be freed from their paradox by cooperation. On the other hand, the absoluteness of the 0 and ∞ that is contained within life and exists at the end of the space-time might strongly support and constrain the life phenomena explained as the cooperation of 0 and ∞ due to the

ambivalence. (For instance, is it possible to describe such a mechanism as a degree of torsion?)

In the concentric dissipative structure model, it seems that the fractal dimension, the principle of dissipative structure, and the volume ratio are related. This is thought to be related to the possibilities that there is recurrence in a connection between 0 and ∞ , and the dynamic equilibrium between the boundaries of the system is scale-free, and that the edge of chaos becomes most functional when it is scale-free. This is thought to be because the dynamic equilibrium of the system corresponds to the relative entropy gradient of the dissipative structure. Then how about using the relative entropy gradient when considering the fourth dimension about the world of life phenomena? This presents a highly interesting perspective. Also, the reversal of the coordinate axes of opposing systems and the harmony of the recursion are related to dynamic equilibrium, recursion relation, and the dynamics of double helix structures, but they seem to represent the versatility of the description model of the communication system of entropy and space-time through the cooperative renormalization of external and internal emergence by cooperation of 0 and ∞ by combination and separation of dimensions.

Life phenomena are characterized by following descriptions.

1. The differentiability of -1 and 1 in fluctuation
2. Recognition of the internal and external contradiction and adaptively organize the spatiotemporal paths in fluctuations, and interact each other adaptively
3. Connecting the dimension in the nonlinear dynamics of fluctuation in space-time
4. Expanding self-similar scales in space-time
5. Adaptively organizing ambivalence through the mechanism that they can only exist as a paradoxical way of being for the renormalization of relativity of entropy in existence and recognition
6. oriented to and requested from deepening relative dissipative structures in the fluctuations of internal and external changes
7. Trying to move away from various paradoxes (entropy and space-time, nothingness and eternity, convergence and diffusion, symmetry disorder, the law of increasing entropy and observation problem and self-referentiality)

These characteristics define life as a dynamic, recursive, and gradual phenomenon.

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